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POLICY BRIEF

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Challenges of the Calamansi Industry in Oriental Mindoro: Marketing Management and Postharvest Handling

Background

The inherent appealing physical attributes of calamansi (*Citrofortunella microcarpa*) from Oriental Mindoro are the same attracting features for its consumers in the Philippine local markets. According to consumers, the calamansi of Oriental Mindoro has a thicker rind, more robust taste, longer shelf-life, and resists weight loss (Department of Agriculture, 2012).

Calamansi is one of the easy-to-find condiments used almost in every popular dish prepared in the Philippines (Morte & Acero, 2017). It is a valuable agricultural product that is converted into various forms, raw, juiced, or processed (Pabuayon, 2000), and fruit that has various contributions to human health (Singh, Singh, Kaur, & Singh, 2020), (Husni, Yeni, & Dachriyanus, 2021), (Siner, Sevanesan, Ambomai, Wahab, & Lasem, 2020).

Notwithstanding the economic value of calamansi in broad facets, this product still lacks support in terms of marketing management and postharvest handling, which could redound to extra benefit in the form of additional revenue if given proper attention by the various concerned agencies. In addition, the need to provide new markets and agribusiness technologies for calamansi products, such as cooperatives, processors, commercial establishments, and restaurants, will help in value-adding, especially during peak season (Quijano, Quijano, & Diaz, 2021) is very apparent.

This policy brief is based on the master's thesis of Flordemae V. Ines entitled "Profile, Status, and Prospects of Calamansi Enterprises in Oriental Mindoro: Basis for Proposed Intervention of Stakeholder Agencies," a study that determined the profile, status, and prospects of calamansi enterprises in Oriental Mindoro that serve as the basis for intervention of stakeholder agencies. She works as Research Assistant at Mindoro State University (formerly MinSCAT) for the SEARCA project Upgrading the Calamansi Value Chain Towards Improving the Calamansi Industry of Oriental Mindoro while

writing the thesis in 2018. Currently, she is a faculty member of the College of Business and Management.

This policy brief focuses on (1) the status of calamansi enterprises in terms of farm practices, post-harvest practices, volume of production, and distribution channel; (2) the extent of prospects of calamansi enterprises in terms of expansion, processing, and enterprise development; and (3) policy recommendations to address the gaps in marketing management and postharvest handling.

Findings

Status of calamansi enterprises in terms of (1) farm practices; (2) post-harvest practices; (3) volume of production, and (4) distribution channel

(1) Most calamansi farmers of Oriental Mindoro preferred budded calamansi as planting materials using calamandarin as rootstock. Calamansi farms are rainfed-dependent, and irrigation is not introduced. Intercropping with banana, lanzones, and coconut with the spacing of four (4) meters apart is a usual practice. To increase the production yield, calamansi farmers practice pruning at least once a year, apply inorganic fertilizer most of the time, manually remove the weeds and control the infestation of pests and diseases through their traditional practices. Fruit pickers are hired during the harvest period and dispose of or sell their produce later on the same day;

(2) Calamansi enterprises in Oriental Mindoro have a good post-harvest practice done manually without machines. These practices include cleaning, sorting, and grading to help ensure and maintain the buyers' preferred quality, improve its marketable appearance, reduce storage losses, prolong the shelf life, and command a higher price. In addition, they prefer to use "kaing" (a large woven bamboo basketlike container designed to contain calamansi and other citrus products for transport) to maintain bruise-free calamansi fruits;

(3) During peak season in Oriental Mindoro, the average production volume of calamansi per hectare reaches 3,261.08 kilograms, while 761.82 kilograms per hectare during the lean season. In 2015, the average production volume reached 3,026.31 kilograms. A marked decrease of 850.58 kilograms per hectare in 2016 was noted as an after-effect of typhoon Nona and infestation of pests and diseases. In 2017, the average production of calamansi was 2,968.14 kilograms per hectare;

(4) The majority of 68% of calamansi farmers in Oriental Mindoro are selling their produce to an assembler (not a middle man per se but a person who gathers or buys calamansi and transports the product to large markets outside the province) with the average price of Php 11.47 per kilo during peak season and Php 24.82 during the lean season. Assembler delivers the calamansi in Divisoria, Manila, and Tanauan, Batangas.

Extent of prospects of calamansi enterprises in terms of expansion, processing, and enterprise development

Based on the study results, calamansi farmers can still expand their business prospects in the calamansi production area. There are bare lands in the province that are left uncultivated, which could be converted into calamansi farms. They may also explore value-adding techniques in their business prospects concerning processing ventures because there are plenty of opportunities for calamansi enterprise development.

Policy Recommendations

These recommendations were made based on the previous study mentioned in this policy brief.

1. Development of coordinated approaches to sustain calamansi enterprising

The non-farmer stakeholders in the calamansi industry, primarily composed of government agencies, should provide solid support to calamansi farmers and their households. Young members of these families should be encouraged to explore the enterprising opportunities in calamansi by first teaching them to appreciate and support it as a sustainable agricultural industry, given the business opportunities and avenues for expanding production areas. Youth should be encouraged to take Agriculture or Entrepreneurship courses to keep the tradition and fashion of farming families for agricultural ventures.

Calamansi farmers, on the other hand, are aware of their limited capacities. Therefore, they acknowledge the importance of various related interventions that are not limited to helping them access credit opportunities for ventures, technical training, and extension support (Amparo, et al., 2017) which some government agencies and the academe could provide.

Extension support through training and seminars should focus on avoiding wastage and post-harvest losses through calamansi processing and other value-adding techniques, especially during peak season.

2. Entrusting special support functions to government agencies

Concerned government agencies should assist in the production, processing, and marketing of calamansi. The Department of Agriculture (DA), through the provincial office and municipal offices, should refocus its concern on the local calamansi industry by conducting a regular review of the industry performance, redesigning programs and interventions that are not fitted to the current situation, and encourage farmers to utilize uncultivated lands for calamansi farming. The Department of Trade and Industry (DTI) should facilitate or recommend training based on current technology and market trends, particularly those that integrate good manufacturing practices (GMP). The academe or Mindoro State University (MinSU) as an academic and R, D, and E institution should advance in developing more calamansi byproducts and development of technology support. Regular conduct of capacity needs assessment to accelerate the calamansi value chain. Local government units (LGUs) should include calamansi industry support in their Annual Investment Plan (AIP) and provide or secure funds for its implementation.

3. Development of support mechanism for locally produced calamansi byproducts

The local government units of Oriental Mindoro should implement a strict policy on the consumption of locally produced calamansi byproducts – a “tangkilikin ang sariling atin” approach. Implementation of this will spur up local calamansi enterprising and development. This protectionist strategy needed to elevate and expand the calamansi value chain to a greater height.

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